

Halogenation. Part VIII. Bromination and Iodination of Monochlorotoluenes.

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The action of bromine on chlorotoluenes has been studied before (Leonard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 570; Jackson and Field, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1879, 1, 162). Cohen and Smithells studied the action of bromine on *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-chlorotoluenes in presence of amalgamated aluminium and obtained several isomeric chlorobromotoluenes (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1911). Other chlorobromotoluenes have been obtained mostly by indirect methods. Direct iodination of chlorotoluenes does not seem to have been studied before; most of the chloriodotoluenes have been obtained by indirect methods only.

We have brominated *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorotoluenes in presence of acetic acid, nitric acid or sulphuric acid. *o*-Chlorotoluene yields 2-chloro-5-bromotoluene, while *m*-chlorotoluene yields 3-chloro-4-bromotoluene and 3-chloro-6-bromotoluene in the proportion of about 3:1. With *p*-chlorotoluene, however, *p*-chlorobenzal bromide is obtained.

o-Chlorotoluene and *m*-chlorotoluene have been iodinated in presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid or a mixture of nitrosulphonic and fuming nitric acid and yielded 2-chloro-5-iodotoluene and 3-chloro-6-iodotoluene respectively. *p*-Chlorotoluene is not iodinated under these conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o- or *m*-Chlorotoluene (10 c.c.) and bromine (6.5 c.c.) were heated together on a water-bath with a reflux condenser with 16 c.c. of acetic acid, 4 c.c. of strong nitric acid or 2 c.c. of fuming nitric or fuming sulphuric acid were added about $\frac{1}{2}$ c.c. at a time at an interval of 10 minutes from the top of the condenser. After heating for 2-4 hours, the product of the reaction was washed with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and the dried product distilled under

reduced pressure, when *o*-chlorotoluene distilled at 83°/12 mm. and 2-chloro-5-bromotoluene at 90-93°/12 mm. Acetic acid and nitric acid yield about 4.8 to 5.5 c.c. of the chloro-bromo product, fuming sulphuric acid gives lower yield. With acetic acid the best yield is at the boiling point of chlorotoluenes.

Working in the same way with the same quantities, *m*-chlorotoluene yields about 5 c.c. of 3-chloro-6-bromotoluene (b. p. 90°-93°/12 mm.) and 1.5 c.c. of 3-chloro-6-bromotoluene (b. p. 120-25°/15 mm).

o-Chlorotoluene and iodine (5 g. each) were dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and to this solution 2 c.c. of strong or fuming nitric acid or 1 c.c. of nitrosulphonic acid mixture was added (0.2 c.c. at a time) from the top of the condenser, and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. In one experiment sodium nitrite (5 g.) and fuming sulphuric acid (7 c.c.) were added to the acetic acid solution. The yield of 2-chloro-5-iodotoluene is between 3 to 4 c.c. *m*-Chlorotoluene treated in the same way yielded *m*-chloro-6-iodotoluene (4 c.c.).

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